

Online Media Management Processes in Modern Travel Service Enterprises: Pathways to Entrepreneurial Success in Northeastern Thailand

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Abstract

This study examines the administration and management processes of online media in modern travel service businesses, leading to entrepreneurial success in Northeastern Thailand. The objectives were (1) to investigate the perceptions of administrative processes in organizational structure, strategy, management systems, administrative methods, personnel, skills, shared values, and online media management in modern travel services, focusing on advertising, public relations, sales promotion, and personal aspects; (2) to assess entrepreneurial success in terms of finance, customers, internal business processes, and learning and growth; (3) to analyze the pathways of administrative processes and online media management in modern travel services that lead to entrepreneurial success in Northeastern Thailand. The study employed a quantitative research approach and the research instrument was a questionnaire administered to a sample size of 223 modern travel service entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand. Data analysis involved frequency distribution, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and structural equation modeling using Mplus software. The key findings show that the level of administrative processes, online media management, and modern tour services among entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand were all rated as high on average. The level of entrepreneurial success was also rated at a high average level. Moreover, the structural model revealed that: (3.1) Administrative processes had a direct positive influence on entrepreneurial success (path coefficient = 0.425), online media management (path coefficient = 0.931), and modern travel services (path coefficient = 0.240). (3.2) Online media management directly influenced entrepreneurial success (path coefficient = 0.271) and modern travel services (path coefficient = 0.725). (3.3) Modern travel services directly influenced entrepreneurial success (path coefficient = 0.298). (3.4) Administrative processes indirectly influenced entrepreneurial success through online media management (path coefficient = 0.216). (3.5) Administrative processes indirectly influenced entrepreneurial success through modern travel services (path coefficient = 0.072). (3.6) Administrative processes indirectly influenced entrepreneurial success through both online media management and modern travel services (path coefficient = 0.525). These findings provide a model that modern travel service entrepreneurs can adapt to develop their businesses sustainably, considering the specific characteristics of their operational areas in Northeastern Thailand.

Keywords: Online Media Management, Entrepreneurial Success, Modern Travel Services

Introduction

The digital era has revolutionized the tourism service industry, with online media becoming a crucial factor in driving business success, particularly for modern travel service businesses. The management of online media has become essential for creating competitive advantages, attracting customers, and building strong brand identities. From social media platforms to websites and digital advertising, integrating online media into marketing strategies and business operations is vital for the success of entrepreneurs in the tourism sector. As the industry continues to evolve, understanding how to effectively manage digital platforms has become increasingly important for businesses seeking to thrive in the current dynamic environment (Buhalis & Law, 2008).

In 2023, Thailand's tourism sector experienced significant growth. The country welcomed a total of 256,751,743 visitors, comprising 203,094,816 domestic visitors and 53,656,927 international visitors. These visitors generated an overall revenue of 1,582,454.35 million baht, consisting of 643,406.18 million baht from domestic visitors and 939,048.17 million baht from international visitors. Specifically, Northeastern Thailand attracted 33,944,232 visitors, including 31,948,865 domestic visitors and 1,995,367 international visitors. This region generated total revenue of 61,556.50 million baht, with 55,953.96 million baht from domestic visitors and 5,602.54 million baht from international visitors (DOT, 2023).

Effective management processes involve coordinating various activities or tasks efficiently and effectively under the direction of others. These processes are crucial functions of administrators, who must continuously implement them to ensure organizational success and achieve objectives. Efficient work processes and goals require designing optimal working methods as well as allocating tasks according to the specialized expertise of personnel within the organization, aligning with the roles defined by the organization to achieve set goals (Pawai, 2018).

In today's society, characterized by the prevalence of online social media and intense competition, businesses utilize platforms such as Facebook, Line, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram for competitive advantage. This shift reflects changing consumer behaviors in the digital age, with increased internet accessibility contributing to the growth of Thailand's e-commerce market. Consequently, tourism businesses have adapted their management strategies to align with customer behaviors and needs, aiming to enhance brand awareness and meet customer demands more effectively (Wongsit, 2019).

Business success relies on efficient management to plan and execute operations effectively. Achieving an organization's vision and objectives requires concrete goals that align all levels of operation in a unified direction. Conducting various business activities while optimizing limited resources under systematic management leads to successful business administration. This approach helps businesses operate in a structured, planned manner with clear objectives, supporting tourism businesses in meeting their goals as part of the overall management process (Multa, 2020).

Common issues faced by tourism business operators include the use of illegal tour guides and instances of tourist deception. Some operators also engage in nominee businesses with foreigners, posing significant national-level problems. These challenges necessitate the development of systematic management approaches for tour businesses in Thailand, requiring cooperation between tourism business operators and the government to establish unified practices for the country (Pawai, 2018).

Given these challenges and opportunities, this research aims to examine the administrative processes and online media management in modern travel service businesses that lead to entrepreneurial success in Northeastern Thailand. The study seeks

to enhance organizational excellence, fostering competitive potential and growth that aligns with tourist demands and adapts to changing factors and environments affecting tourism. The findings will contribute to developing future organizational strategies for tourism businesses and provide valuable information for relevant agencies to enhance Thailand's tourism competitiveness on a global scale.

Research Objectives:

1. To investigate the perceptions of administrative processes and online media management in modern travel service businesses in Northeastern Thailand
2. To assess the level of entrepreneurial success among modern travel service businesses in Northeastern Thailand, considering financial, customer, internal business processes, and learning and growth aspects
3. To analyze the direct and indirect pathways through which administrative processes and online media management influence entrepreneurial success in the context of modern travel services in Northeastern Thailand

Relevant Theoretical Concepts

The concept of management processes involves utilizing both science and art to employ administrative resources in achieving predetermined objectives efficiently. Management is closely related to policy formulation and implementation. In the context of this research, the focus is on business administration or private sector management, where the primary objective is profit maximization (Saengpetch, 2019). Effective management processes require appropriate strategies, organizational structures, and tourism management systems, as well as knowledgeable, skilled, and experienced tourism personnel with positive attitudes toward their work. Tourism management should be tailored to local contexts and involve knowledge exchange, opinion sharing, and experience transfer to promote sustainable tourism growth (Khamprasert et al., 2018).

The concept of online media management encompasses two-way communication channels, information exchange, and interactions between senders and receivers, including the sharing of various media through the Internet. Social media networks have become integral to daily life across all age groups due to advancements in computer technology and internet accessibility. These platforms have expanded their user base and broadened their significance, offering diverse communication channels for accessing information, news, and products through static images, videos, audio, and multimedia formats (Kasemsawat, 2018). Kim and Park (2020) corroborate this, highlighting social media's role as a marketing tool and noting that businesses utilize platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter to enhance visibility and connect with customers, enabling direct interaction with tourists.

The concept of service refers to activities or processes carried out by individuals, legal entities, or business organizations to provide utility, value, assistance, or convenience to service recipients. The objective is to meet user needs, ensure satisfaction, create a memorable organizational image, and help the organization achieve its business goals and objectives (Kawiset, 2019).

The thought of entrepreneurial success involves measuring business performance through both financial and non-financial metrics. Non-financial performance indicators serve as management tools and contribute to financial success. Entrepreneurial success is achieved by efficiently managing resources and applying knowledge and skills in business activities to meet goals (Kootrakool, 2018). Chen and Tseng (2022) and Lam and Lee (2021) offer a strategic perspective, suggesting that successful online media management

involves not only customer engagement but also dedicated digital marketing teams and clear strategies for long-term business success.

The concept of tourism context posits that tourism contributes to economic and social development while promoting cultural awareness. It provides relaxation, experiences, and relationship-building opportunities for travelers. Sustainable tourism operates within the limits of nature, community, traditions, culture, and local ways of life. It emphasizes community participation and equitable distribution of economic benefits among stakeholders, while respecting local guidance in tourism areas (Kajonpai, 2016).

Research Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis:

To study the management and online media management processes of modern travel service businesses that lead to the success of entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, which is consistent and harmonious with empirical data.

Research Methodology

Population and Sample

The study population comprised 500 modern travel service business entrepreneurs operating in the Northeastern region of Thailand in 2023. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula (1973) at a 95% confidence level with a $\pm 5\%$ margin of error, yielding 223 respondents. Simple random sampling was employed to select participants from a list provided by the Department of Tourism, ensuring a representative sample and minimizing selection bias.

Geographical Scope

The study focused on the Northeastern region of Thailand, encompassing 20 provinces with high tourism potential and a significant concentration of modern travel service businesses. Key provinces included Khon Kaen, Udon Thani, Ubon Ratchathani, and Nakhon Ratchasima.

Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire, utilizing a 5-point Likert scale, served as the primary research instrument. The questionnaire was developed based on a comprehensive review of relevant national and international literature. Content validity was assessed by three subject-matter experts, and internal consistency reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, with coefficients ranging from .81 to .93, indicating high reliability.

The questionnaire comprised five sections:

1. Demographic Information (e.g., gender, age, business experience)
2. Administrative Process (7 dimensions, 41 items)
3. Online Media Management (4 dimensions, 24 items)
4. Modern Tour Services (single item)
5. Entrepreneurial Success (4 dimensions, 22 items)

Data Collection

Data were collected between April and June 2023 using both online (Google Forms) and paper-based questionnaires. Participants received an informed consent form and a cover letter explaining the study's purpose. Participation was voluntary.

Preliminary Data Screening

Two main procedures were conducted prior to statistical analysis:

1. Normality: Skewness values ranged from -1.202 to -0.469 , and kurtosis values ranged from -0.857 to 1.388 , indicating acceptable normal distribution (Brown, 2015; Kline, 2015).
2. Multicollinearity: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values ranged from 1.503 to 8.081 , and Tolerance values ranged from 0.124 to 0.665 ,

within acceptable thresholds (VIF < 10, Tolerance > 0.10) as suggested by James et al. (2017) and Soewignyo (2020).

Data Analysis

The following analytical techniques were employed:

1. Descriptive Statistics: Frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to describe sample characteristics and variable tendencies.
2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): Utilized to assess construct validity and the fit between observed variables and latent constructs.
3. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): Employed to evaluate causal relationships among exogenous, mediating, and endogenous variables.

The analysis was performed using Mplus software. Model fit indices reported included:

- Chi-square (χ^2)
- Comparative Fit Index (CFI)
- Tucker–Lewis Index (TLI)
- Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)
- Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)

Model fit was evaluated based on the following thresholds (Hair et al., 2010): CFI and TLI > .90, RMSEA < .08, SRMR < .08, and $\chi^2/df < 5$.

Empirical Results

The research findings are presented as follows:

1. Management Processes of Modern Travel Service Business Entrepreneurs

Table 1 presents the means and standard deviations of management processes for modern travel service business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand.

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations of Management Processes

Management Process	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Level
Organizational Structure	4.22	0.67	High
Strategy	4.23	0.67	High
Management Systems	4.09	0.70	High
Management Style	4.12	0.73	High
Staff	4.11	0.68	High
Skills	4.17	0.65	High
Shared Values	4.12	0.68	High
Overall	4.15	0.57	High

Source: Calculated

The overall level of management processes was high (M = 4.15, SD = 0.57). All aspects were rated high, with Strategy (M = 4.23, SD = 0.67) and Organizational Structure (M = 4.22, SD = 0.67) scoring the highest, while Management Systems (M = 4.09, SD = 0.70) scored the lowest.

2. Online Media Management

Table 2 illustrates the means and standard deviations of online media management practices.

Table 2: Online Media Management Practices

Online Media Management	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Level
Advertising	4.12	0.75	High
Public Relations	4.19	0.68	High
Sales Promotion	4.16	0.77	High
Personal Selling	4.16	0.77	High
Overall	4.16	0.68	High

Source: Calculated

The overall level of online media management was high (M = 4.16, SD = 0.68). All dimensions were rated high, with Public Relations (M = 4.19, SD = 0.68) scoring the highest and Advertising (M = 4.12, SD = 0.75) the lowest.

3. Modern Tour Service Provision

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation for modern tour service provision.

Table 3: Modern Tour Service Provision

Modern Tour Service Provision	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Level
Providing modern tour services	4.35	0.79	High
Overall	4.35	0.79	High

Source: Calculated

The provision of modern tour services was rated high (M = 4.35, SD = 0.79).

4. Business Success Levels

Table 4 illustrates the means and standard deviations of business success levels.

Table 4: Business Success Levels

Business Success Levels	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Level
Financial	4.13	0.74	High
Customer	4.13	0.73	High
Internal Business Process	4.11	0.69	High
Learning and Development	4.29	0.54	High
Overall	4.17	0.60	High

The overall level of business success was high (M = 4.17, SD = 0.60). All dimensions were rated high, with Learning and Development (M = 4.29, SD = 0.54) scoring the highest and Internal Business Process (M = 4.11, SD = 0.69) the lowest.

Analysis of Measurement Models

The measurement model analysis, utilizing confirmatory factor analysis for the success factors of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, demonstrated consistency with empirical data after adjustments, without necessitating the removal of any indicators from the measurement model. The construct reliability of the variables satisfied the criteria at 0.992, surpassing the threshold of 0.6. The construct validity (Pv) was 0.969, exceeding the required threshold of 0.5. The model fit indices were as follows: $\chi^2 = 1.260$, $df = 1$, $\chi^2/df = 1.260$, $p\text{-value} = 0.2617$, $CFI = 1.000$, $TLI = 0.998$, $RMSEA = 0.034$, and $SRMR = 0.007$.

According to Hair et al. (2010), the convergent validity assessment should meet the following specified criteria: factor loadings should be 0.50 or higher, the variance extracted should be 0.50 or higher, and the construct reliability should be 0.60 or higher.

The analysis results indicated that the factor loadings of the variables met the standard criteria, with values of 0.913, 0.885, 0.800, 0.789, 0.775, 0.738, and 0.673, respectively. These values are considered acceptable based on the measures of construct reliability (Pc) and construct validity.

Structural Model Analysis

The analysis of causal path influences in the adjusted linear structural equation model elucidates the relationships between management processes, modern online media management, and tourism service businesses, contributing to entrepreneurial success in Northeastern Thailand, as illustrated in Table 5.

Table 5: Goodness of Fit Indices for the Structural Equation Model with Empirical Data

Test Statistics	Modified Model (Post-Adjustment)	Standard Criteria
p-value	0.0675	> 0.05
χ^2 / df	3.230	< 5.0
CFI	0.962	> 0.90
TLI	0.943	> 0.90
RMSEA	0.48	< 0.05
SRMR	0.031	< 0.05

(Hair et al., 2010)

The results indicate that the modified structural equation model demonstrates a good fit with the empirical data. The p-value (0.0675) exceeds 0.05, suggesting no significant difference between the model and the observed data. The χ^2/df ratio (3.230) is below 5.0, indicating an acceptable fit. Both CFI (0.962) and TLI (0.943) surpass 0.90, demonstrating good comparative fit. The RMSEA (0.048) and SRMR (0.031) are both below 0.05, exhibiting good absolute fit. Collectively, these indices suggest that the modified model adequately represents the relationships among the variables in the study.

As evidenced in Table 5, the structural equation model post-modification exhibits a good fit with the empirical data, supporting the null hypothesis that the theoretical model is consistent with the empirical data. This conclusion is based on the following fit indices:

$$\text{Chi-square } (\chi^2) = 258.401$$

$$\text{Degrees of freedom } (df) = 80$$

$$\text{p-value} = 0.0675$$

$$\text{Relative chi-square } (\chi^2 / df) = 3.230$$

$$\text{Comparative Fit Index (CFI)} = 0.962$$

$$\text{Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)} = 0.943$$

$$\text{Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)} = 0.048$$

$$\text{Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)} = 0.031$$

These fit indices collectively indicate that the modified structural model adequately represents the relationships among the variables in the study. The non-significant p-value ($p > 0.05$) suggests no significant difference between the model-implied covariance matrix and the observed covariance matrix. The relative chi-square value is below

the recommended threshold of 5.0, indicating an acceptable fit. Both CFI and TLI exceed 0.90, demonstrating good comparative fit. The RMSEA and SRMR values are below 0.05, indicating good absolute fit. These results are visually represented in Figure 2 (not provided in the text).

$\chi^2 = 258.401, df = 80, \chi^2 / df = 3.230, p\text{-value} = 0.0675,$
 CFI = 0.962, TLI = 0.943, RMSEA = 0.048, SRMR = 0.031

Figure 2: Structural Equation Model fit with Empirical Data

Table 6: Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Variables

Causal Variable (Effect)	Direct Effect (DE)	Indirect Effect (IE)	Total Effect (TE)	Result
Process – Success	0.425***	-	0.425	Accepted
Online - Success	0.271***	-	0.271	Accepted
Service – Success	0.298***	-	0.298	Accepted
Process – Online	0.931***	-	0.931	Accepted
Process – Service	0.240***	-	0.240	Accepted
Online– Service	0.725***	-	0.725	Accepted
Online - Process – Success	0.271***	0.216***	0.487	Accepted
Service - Process – Success	0.298***	0.072***	0.370	Accepted
Process - Online – Service – Success	0.425***	0.525***	0.950	Accepted

Note: *** indicates statistical significance at $p < 0.01$

Legend:

Process: Management Process

Online: Online Media Management

Service: Modern Tourism Service
 Success: Business Entrepreneur Success

This table presents the direct effects (DE), indirect effects (IE), and total effects (TE) of the causal relationships between variables in the structural equation model. All relationships demonstrate statistical significance at the 0.01 level, supporting the acceptance of the hypothesized pathways. The total effects represent the sum of direct and indirect effects, providing a comprehensive view of the influence of each variable on business entrepreneur success in the context of modern tourism services and online media management.

The results of the hypothesis testing, as shown in Table 6, indicate that the administrative and management processes of modern online tourism businesses leading to entrepreneurial success in Northeastern Thailand are consistent with empirical data. Specifically:

1. The administrative process has a direct positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.425.

2. The administrative process has a direct positive influence on online media management, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.931.

3. The administrative process has a direct positive influence on the provision of modern tourism services, with a statistically significant level of .01 and a path coefficient of 0.240.

4. Online media management has a direct positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.271.

5. Online media management has a direct positive influence on the provision of modern tourism services, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.725.

6. The provision of modern tourism services has a direct positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, with a statistically significant level of .01 and a path coefficient of 0.298.

7. The administrative process has an indirect positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, through the pathway of online media management, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.216.

8. The administrative process has an indirect positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, through the pathway of the provision of modern tourism services, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.072.

9. The administrative process has an indirect positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, through the pathways of both online media management and the provision of modern tourism services, with a statistically significant level of 0.01 and a path coefficient of 0.525.

In summary, the results of the direct and indirect influence analysis and hypothesis testing support the following:

H1: The administrative process has a direct positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand.

- H2 : Online media management has a direct positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand.
- H3: The provision of modern tourism services has a direct positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand.
- H4: The administrative process has an indirect positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, through the pathway of online media management.
- H5: The administrative process has an indirect positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, through the pathway of the provision of modern tourism services.
- H6: The administrative process has an indirect positive influence on the success of business entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand, through the pathways of both online media management and the provision of modern tourism services.

Research Discussion

The research findings present several critical issues for discussion (Singnuan & Teerasukittikul, 2020; Nangkhalaphiwat, 2014; Thongrod, 2019; Pawai, 2018; Khamprasoet et al., 2018).

1. The modern business administration processes of the tourism industry in Northeastern Thailand. The research revealed that the business administration processes of modern tourism service providers, in terms of strategy, organizational structure, skills, management methods, shared values, personnel, and management systems, are at a good level. This is because businesses have clear strategies and conceptual frameworks to develop the business and achieve their goals, leading to better competitiveness. They have adapted their organizational structures to align with the changing environment, defined the authority and responsibilities according to the structure, and utilized modern technologies in their operations based on the appropriateness of their plans. The tourism attractions have disseminated information through personal media, and have instilled a sense of conservation of resources and the environment in all stakeholders. They provide services with politeness, neatness, and friendliness, and have organized campaigns to educate tourists on environmental conservation, which is consistent with the research of Singnuan and Teerasukittikul (2020) on the community-based sustainable agricultural tourism management in Sakaeo Province and the research Nangkhalaphiwat (2014) on the preparation of Thailand's tourism workforce to support the integration into the ASEAN Economic Community.

2. The online media management of modern tourism service providers. The research found that the online media management of modern tourism service providers, in terms of public relations, sales promotion, personnel, and advertising, is at a good level. This is because tourism businesses use online media to persuade customers to demand their products or services, provide details about the convenience of travel or service facilities, offer online payment options to facilitate customers, have staff to provide information about products or services through online media and use online media to persuade customers to demand their products or services. This is consistent with the research of Thongrod (2018) on the management of agricultural tourism, boat cruises along the Maha Sawat Canal in Phutthamonthon District, Nakhon Pathom Province, which found that tourists visited the boat cruise along the Maha Sawat Canal because of the farmers' way of life and the natural environment, and they obtained information about the tourism from the internet/website/social media.

3. The success of tourism service providers in Northeastern Thailand. The research found out that the success of tourism service providers in Northeastern Thailand, in terms

of learning and growth, finance, customers, and internal processes, is at a good level. This is because the businesses provide quality services and are attentive to the needs of their customers, monitor their performance for learning and strategy development, achieve their operational objectives, provide services to all customers or consumer groups equally and comprehensively, and continuously develop in line with innovations and new technologies. This is consistent with the research of Pawai (2018) on the management approaches to enhance the effectiveness of tour businesses in Thailand, which revealed that the overall management factors of tour businesses are significantly related to the overall effectiveness of tour business management at the 0.01 level of statistical significance, with planning, organizing, controlling, and leadership having influences that affect the effectiveness of tour business management and can jointly explain 74.2% of the changes in tour business management effectiveness (Adjusted R Square = 0.742).

4. The management processes and online media management of modern tourism service providers that lead to the success of entrepreneurs in Northeastern Thailand are due to the businesses having clearly defined roles and responsibilities for each department, having appropriate service systems, developing organizational structures, managing work systems, and managing structures and administration systems appropriately. They involve tourists in the process of thinking and planning tourism sites, disseminate information through advertising media, radio, or television, and have responsible staff who provide equitable service and have sufficient knowledge and skills to meet the needs of users. This is consistent with the findings of a study by Khamprasoet et al. (2018), which examined the community participation in tourism management in the Akkarad drum-making village, Pa Mok District, Ang Thong Province, and discovered that government agencies integrated various activities with other communities, had plans to promote tourism and develop products concurrently, and continuously promoted the destination.

Recommendations for Implementing the Research Findings

Theoretical Contributions

This research has made a theoretical contribution by developing a new conceptual framework for studying the online business management and administrative processes that lead to entrepreneurial success in the modern tourism service industry. This research framework was developed through a comprehensive review of the literature and can be applied or adapted for use in similar research studies.

Practical Contributions

Based on the research findings, the following practical recommendations are proposed:

1. Performance standards should be designed with the needs of tourists as the central focus, and these standards should be regularly established and reviewed to ensure they adequately encompass the requirements of the tourist clientele.
2. The organization's information systems should be continuously developed to provide higher-quality services and formats that better match the demands and preferences of consumers.
3. The organizational structure and operational systems should be adjusted regularly to ensure alignment with the agency's strategic plans and objectives.

4. Tourist attractions ought provide detailed documentation or brochures outlining the various activities and offerings available to visitors.
5. The management of tourist attractions should be structured in a manner that facilitates the distribution of revenue to the local communities.
6. A systematic process must be in place to assess the impact and overall success of the organization's operations.

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